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Content and Significance of the Concept of Drugs

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Abstract:

This article reveals the content and essence of the concept of drug addiction, which is a negative scourge in today's globalization and modernization. Its main focus is on the restoration of the original meaning of the words "drug addiction", "drug trafficking", "addiction", its etymology, genesis, "as a social threat" as a phenomenon contrary to human life. The problem is also studied on the basis of a retrospective history, world religions, ancient Greek scholars, and the work done in recent times on the basis of a comprehensive, systematic analysis. Along with theoretical views, scientific-analytical, scientific-practical, pragmatic conclusions are given.

Keywords: drugs, drug trafficking (called NON) Drug prevention, "narcotics", anesthesia, fear, person and society, disability,

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INTRODUCTION

From the epiphenomenon of various “moral interventions” in the second half of the twentieth century, drug addiction became a constant practice of modern civilization, and by the end of the twentieth century, the drug trade (hereinafter referred to as NON) had become a real threat to all mankind. The global nature of the new form of social risk allows us to emphasize that international institutions and most countries do not have an effective mechanism for drug prevention in their anti-drug policies. In the paradigm of drug prevention research, the necessary approach to studying the formation and growing process of human addiction has not yet been developed and applied, there is no socio-philosophical analysis of the impact of postindustrial civilization codes on human intoxication [1].

As a result, a “dangerous society” cannot control its social space, and in a globalizing world, drug addiction has become the biographical image of many resolving “systemic conflicts” [2].

In our view, the revision of the conceptual framework for the study of a new form of global social risk should begin with the restoration of the original meaning of the words “drug addiction”, “drug trafficking”, and “addiction”. Unfortunately, in UN documents and anti-drug laws of many countries, as well as in the scientific literature, they are considered only as distinguishing marks that correspond to differentiated concepts. In other words, to understand the essence of these words, we need to fully understand what is called “external linguistics” by linguist Ferdinand de Saussure. This allows us not only to show the existing physiological, psychological, phenomenological, logical, dialectical, ontological spheres, but also to reveal all possible and understandable meanings of these words, which serve as symbols for different peoples in different periods of history. Ultimately, this allows us to lay the groundwork for a new paradigm for research on drug prevention. The etymology of the words studied is an ancient Greek term for elements whose meanings are almost identical and is the final generalization of the principle of application of ancient Greece to natural elements.

Understanding the attitude of ancient Greece, its weakness in the face of the outside world, allows Plato to use the term “narcissus” now not only in the pure sense of the word, but also as a symbol. Let's look at this in the example of the Menon dialogue, where one of Socrates' interlocutors describes the philosopher's magical influence on him as follows: "And now it seemed to me that you did the same to me - I was embarrassed. In fact, my heart aches and my tongue is pulled out - I don't know how to answer you" [3].

And the word “Narke” does not call for the abstraction of reality expressed by Plato as “anesthesia”, “insomnia”, “convulsions”, but refers to stereotypes of the ancient Greek behavior (dullness, flight, defensive aggression) attached to the gods.

Plato's dialogues are rich in phrases that express a state of fear, horror, and it is difficult to analyze the number of shadows of fear. What is feared inspires “fear”; and he who dares does not inspire “fear”. And “fear” is inspired by what is expected, not by the past, not by the present. Plato also offers countermeasures to meet the security needs of ancient Greece. He appeals to them: to drink plenty of wine on holidays even after 40 years; general dances and songs; the tendency of birds to fight [4].

In the process of language development, the etymology of the ancient Greek word “narke” begins to participate in the word formation of other words using various morphemes. In modern Greek (formed around the 2nd-5th centuries BC) the derivatives of the word’s “drugs” appeared [5].

They identify objects and events in the outside world that evoke a sense of insecurity and fear in the population of the Byzantine Empire. In modern Greek, there is also the compound word “addiction,” formed by the direct addition of the words “narco” and “mania” using the “o” interface. At the same time, the word “mania” is a supporting component in the complex word “addiction,” and the preceding component, “nar,” serves as a determinant of the etymology.

The false term “mania” in Plato has two planned semantics and means “anger”, “madness”. This has a positive meaning only in the Feast and the Phaedra, i.e., only the concept of ideal beauty or ideological art is given in the dialogues. Divine madness, according to Plato, is pure for humans Apollo, Dionysus, Muses, Aphrodite in Heaven and her son Eros [6].

In all other dialogues, the term “mania” has a clear negative connotation, indicating a patient’s condition that requires mandatory treatment. According to Plato, insanity is a manifestation of mental illness and is defined by him as physical and mental illness, savage immorality, anger, rage, evil deeds of soul and body, or even simply stupidity [7].

Therefore, the philosopher believes that a person’s behavior is insane if it is characterized by unfounded passions and lusts such as thirst for wealth, gambling, laughter, flirtatious dances, jealousy, excessive intoxication, nonsense [8].

Intuitive pleasures are depicted in dialogues in the form of mythological beasts - Kimera, Skilla and Kerber. Plato the Great not only characterizes the sick soul, but also analyzes the mechanism of the onset of the disease. The chariot of the human soul becomes it in two cases: the chariot driver's inability to cope with the "death part of the soul"; the ruthlessness of the chariot itself. Given that the spirit of Plato does not have serious materiality, but has an absolute and semantic content, we have every reason to say that the philosopher spoke of a “true homeland of the human soul” that is not in the ideal world.

Knowing the mechanism of formation of the complex name "addiction", a sufficient understanding of the subject of its causal basis, allows us to emphasize that when the word "addiction" appeared, it means that a person is an idolater in front of the outside world. However, from spoken Greek, the term was gradually replaced by the ancient Greek word for “idolatry,” and it was later forgotten for hundreds of years. A similar fate is associated with the term “drugs”.

Linguistic-etymological, historical-semiological and comparative analysis of the concepts of "drug addiction" and "drug addiction" allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. In modern Greek, the compound word "addiction" appeared much later than the name "addiction";
2. The need to know and understand it was connected with the social phenomenon in the Byzantine language - the desire to express idolatry by new linguistic means;

3. In modern Greek, the lexemes “drug” and “narcotics” became synonyms from the ancient Greek words meaning “idolat”, “idolater”;

4. In the Old Testament, the first pagans were called Jews, who after the liberation from Egyptian captivity in the eighteenth century BC again began to worship idols of profit and wealth. They offered sacrifices to the golden calf and said, "Behold, your God Israel, who brought you out of Egypt!" (From the Bible).

5. The Bible considers it idolatry to rule over the human body. His enslavement to the boiling world, listening to his evil deeds. And the mysterious words of the Apostle John “about the light shining in the darkness,” “the whole world lies in evil,” is not a mere religious form, but a serious and bitter truth that evil is inherent in the world and human nature. In Christian theology, pride, greed, adultery (lust), envy, anger, and indifference (negligence) all point to the seven deadly sins of man. In Orthodoxy, the sins that a sinner is punished during severe trials include: lying, slander, greed, laziness, theft, lying, jealousy, pride, bad memory, anger, murder, abomination, adultery, adultery. Heresy is not a mercy, but a sin committed through this word [9].

What is commanded to be good in Islamic teaching is good, and what is commanded to be bad is bad. The precepts of our religion forbid man from all things that cause harm to his religion, soul, mind, lineage, and health, and, in general, his life, from those things, declaring them not only to return, but to be unclean. One of these is drugs. After all, addiction is the enemy of the future of mankind. Allah says in Surat al-A'raf 157: "... He enjoins what is right and forbids what is wrong, and makes lawful what is good and forbids what is impure".

It is said in a hadith: "Everything that intoxicates is haram." Another hadith says, "Whoever kills himself with poison will suffer the fire of Hell on the Day of Resurrection".

To the question of some people, "Are the names of drugs not mentioned in the verses and hadiths?", This is one of the miracles of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him). In one word, he said, "Any intoxicant or detoxifier is unclean." It is known that no matter what the drugs are called, they have the quality of intoxication and relaxation of the body.

God commands people not to commit suicide and not to shed the blood of others unjustly. The drug, on the other hand, would be suicidal by consuming substances that would eventually lead to death. It is narrated in a hadith: "Whoever kills himself with something, he will be tormented in Hell on the Day of Resurrection." It was narrated on the authority of al-Bukhari that the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: “Allah says (interpretation of the meaning)” [10]. While the cost of drugs causes economic damage to both the individual and society, it is also a waste. Consumption of these substances leads to a waste of wealth and wealth.

Waste, on the other hand, is forbidden by the Qur'an and hadiths, and it leads to humiliation.

The following can be said about the damage to health. Modern scientific advances prove the dangers of drugs. These include the gradual development of serious diseases and irreversible serious diseases of the internal organs. The drug adversely affects the activity of the human stomach, liver, lungs. It also leads to human nervousness and thus the loss of the ability to see, hear, smell, think, feel hot and cold, hard and soft, sweet and savory.

The harm they do to society is so great that the addict loses interest, importance, and concern for himself or herself, then for his or her family, profession, or education. It is especially sad that young people, who are the main force of progress in production, are the first victims of drug addiction.

Addiction leads to a breakdown in the relationship between the individual and society. In fact, we often see it in our lives today. It is a fact of life that drug addicts are separated from their relatives, children, and spouses, and often have children with disabilities. When a drug is unclean, both its sale and its commercial benefits are considered unclean.

In a hadith, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said, "Lord! When I grow old, you will increase my sustenance". It is not difficult to understand from the content of this hadith that it is very important for a person to eat the grief of old age from a young age, to protect himself from alcoholism and drug addiction, and to avoid being humiliated in old age.

In the early twentieth century, the terms "drugs" and "addiction" returned to European languages. This, in our opinion, is explained by the following cases: from the second half of the XIX century, anesthesia began to be widely used in medicine; At the end of the 19th century, the founder of psychoanalysis, S. Freud discovered a physical and mental attachment to cocaine; at present, within the framework of nation-states, medical and epidemic forms of opiumism, cocaineism, morphinism are being formed, the social space of which is constantly globalizing; and finally, the desire of society is not only to know the true mechanism of the emergence and development of addiction to intoxicants, but also to resist it effectively.

To this end, in 1909, the international community adopted a multilateral agreement on the control of opium, cocaine, cannabis and others. At an international conference on opium in 1912, under pressure from the medical community, they were called drugs. The conference also approved a list of the first drugs in human history.

Given that the symptoms of drug addiction, such as mania, opioids, narcotics, heroin, are the same, the World Health Organization (founded in 1948) has identified all forms of disease caused by non-medical use of substances included in the list of drugs included in the general concept of "addiction". A patient who is addicted to drugs is distinguished from a healthy person by the presence of inactivity, mental and physical dependence syndromes [11].

In the early second half of the twentieth century, the continual disintegration of the emotional socio-cultural system led to a type of personality whose behavior in the United States and Western Europe was determined by a sensitive passive cultural mentality. His motto: "Life is short", "Enjoy the day", "Wine, women, song", "Eat, drink, be happy". In a youthful environment, this hippie movement was particularly evident with the emergence and spread of a cultural type of addiction. In other words, addiction becomes a social phenomenon with its own qualitative and quantitative characteristics. These include, first of all, the state and level of addiction in society, the composition and dynamics of addiction, types of addiction. To distinguish "addiction" as a social phenomenon from "addiction" as a disease, the cultural type of addiction is referred to in the scientific literature as the concept of "addiction" [12].

The word "addiction" is derived from the word "addicts", in direct motivational relationships, given that the term "addiction" refers to a class of substances included in the

list of drugs, we use the word "addiction" to refer to a disease or a social phenomenon caused by not using certain drugs for medical purposes. We have every reason to say. This conclusion allows us to prove that the derivative words are hashishism, opiumism, cocainism, morphism, addiction, and so on. Naturally, it belongs to the same word-formation type and has the same word-formation meaning. In other words, they represent a property called hashish, opium, cocaine, drugs, based on lexemes. But what is important to us in both cases is that the concept of addiction refers to the modern form of idolatry of the individual in the category of "existence" or "individualized society" in the sense of "something of its own" in world European languages.

The essence of "addiction" can be defined as "things within" through the syndrome of disintegration of human and social nature, which is characterized by their physical (physical) and spiritual structures, the integrity and dialectical unity of the biosocial system. Its common features are manifested in the avoidance of "positive freedom", economic determinism, technicalism, the institutionalization of science as an "ideology", the expansion of the market in solving all the problems of man, society and nature [13].

Protecting human life and health is one of the social responsibilities. From the first years of independence, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan paid special attention to such negative evils as "drug addiction". In this regard, I.A. Karimov said: "... the fight against drug trafficking and trafficking should become the main direction and content of cooperation between our countries" [14].

According to the analysis of the media, it can be observed that in recent years the geographical breadth of drug use and the proportion of social events related to drug addiction have been increasing.

At the same time, it should be noted that drug addiction is a serious criminogenic phenomenon that contributes to the complication of the ideological and social situation in some regions of the country. In order to eradicate such a negative vice from the life of our society, it is necessary to address a wide range of complex issues, including large-scale socio-political, administrative, medical and other problems. In particular, it is necessary to legally develop the consciousness of our people and to carry out effective propaganda work on a regular basis, if necessary. This, in turn, is a requirement of the times.

Everyone knows the evils of addiction. Everyone is aware that a person who consumes cannabis, opium, marijuana, heroin, opium, or any other type of drug can suffer from chronic pain. Almost every day there are a series of broadcasts and programs, newspapers and articles about the consequences of drug addiction in the media, on the radio and in the mirror-world. But the fight against and prevention of drug addiction, which is dangerous both for society and for human health and the future, is not easy [15].

Drug addiction is one of the negative vices that worries humanity the most today. Complications of the totalitarian regime and a number of objective difficulties in the transition period have led to an increase in drug addiction in our country in recent years, especially heroin.

At the current stage of development of society, the natural consequence of the transition to a market economy is rising unemployment, many leisure activities, temporary disruptions in cultural and educational facilities, sports stadiums, and the complete closure or

commercialization of some of the population [16], especially among young people, is leading to an increase in the use of drugs, leisure time, various domestic and moral disorders, "good living" at the expense of crime, watching videos that promote violence [17].

In this regard, it should be noted that the first stage of scientific knowledge in philosophy is to determine the concept, the essence of the problem under study. This is the axiomatic rule of social cognition [18].

Determining the meaning of terms is of particular importance not only in conducting empirical research, but also in conducting practical activities [19]. One such area is the fight against drug addiction. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to find terms that have a clear meaning, identify the properties of drugs and psychotropic substances that are the subject of the crime, and group them. This serves as a basis for identifying and classifying the description of socially dangerous behavior, identifying the spiritual and educational factors that prevent it.

Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances" adopted on August 19, 1999, describes the essence of the following basic concepts of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances.

Narcotic drugs - drugs or plants of synthetic or natural origin, containing narcotic substances, included in the list of narcotic drugs and controlled in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Psychotropic substances - substances of synthetic or natural origin included in the list of psychotropic substances and controlled in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Substances used in the manufacture of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances included in the list of *precursors* and controlled in the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Analogs of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances - substances of synthetic or natural origin, similar in composition and properties to narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, which, like them, have an active effect on the psyche;

A drug is a mixture of substances in any physical state containing one or more narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances;

Circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors - import (export), transfer, storage, issuance, sale, distribution, receipt, transportation, shipment, development, production, preparation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors their use and destruction, as well as the cultivation of plants containing narcotic substances;

Addiction (drug addiction) - a disease associated with mental and physical dependence on drugs;

Addiction (toxicomania) is a disease associated with psycho-physical dependence on psychotropic substances, as well as substances that have no medicinal properties, are of synthetic or natural origin, and have an active effect on the psyche, similar to drugs.

In our opinion, if this law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is supplemented with the following additions, it would be expedient to give more space to the spiritual and educational factors in the fight against the use of drugs, psychotropic substances, precursors and other drugs by young people.

Article 3 of the law, entitled "Basic Concepts", shows that some terms, in particular "addiction", are clearly defined, while other terms require a more precise definition. In our opinion, it is expedient to include in the legal definition of a drug its medical criteria as well.

(We will discuss this issue later, and finally we are now faced with the task of analyzing, determining, the interaction of different concepts).

Determining the content and interdependence of the concepts of "addiction", "drug addiction" and "narcotism" is theoretically important and unique. Such definitions are important not only from a terminological point of view, but also because of the understanding of the nature of such negative phenomena and the connection of legal regulation with the act, "drug", "mood of addiction", "juvenile addiction", "addiction" "crime" and a number of other criteria.

In our opinion, the study of this problem should consider that the terms "drug addiction", "drug addict" used in medicine (mostly narcology), are equally important not only for medical professionals, but also for philosophers, lawyers, sociologists, educators, politicians.

In addition, these terms are also related to legal legislation, which cannot be used unreasonably from a medical point of view. Therefore, understanding a drug-related behavior that is dangerous to society only from a medical point of view leads to further errors. We believe that it is important to study this issue from a socio-philosophical, spiritual-enlightenment, psychological point of view.

For this reason, it is also important to define the meaning of the term "drug" because its consumption leads to drug addiction.

It is known that in nature and medicine there are a large number of different substances that have a strong effect on the whole organism, brain, nervous system, psyche. Such substances, which are natural or artificial in origin, have the property of having an active effect on a person's psyche when combined with herbal preparations, psychoactive substances or other substances that poison the brain.

So far, scientists and practitioners have been studying drugs that have a high social risk among the substances that actively affect the psyche of an individual, that is, drugs that cause widespread harm to society and those who consume and distribute it.

The official legal criterion is that certain drugs are specified in international law or domestic laws of the state, which have a normative character, in official lists. Without the above criteria, this or that drug cannot be considered a drug. The substantive criterion is the inclusion of a substance in the list of drugs, while the formal-legal criterion serves as a target for law enforcement agencies in the field under study.

A number of authors believe that the term "narcotics" is synonymous with the term "narcotics" and therefore there was no need to replace the term "narcotics" with the term "narcotics" in the law. Without denying the "similarity" of these terms, we believe that this change is absolutely correct, since the concept of "substance" does not apply to substances that are considered drugs, nor to the lists in international conventions, because not only substances, but also liquids, plants or plants. parts and drugs can also be the subject of addiction. The name of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances" of 1999 also correctly states "drugs".

The term "means" describes the state of things in a relatively clear and complete way. It is therefore very reasonable to include this term in the language of law. Therefore, when

talking about the subject of the crimes provided for in Articles 270-276 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is more appropriate to use the term "drug".

In the literature on criminology, psychology, pedagogy (including articles in the media), the terms "drug", "sedative", "opium" and others can be used in relation to drugs.

CONCLUSION

In general, the following conclusions can be drawn from this article:

- given the global nature of the new form of social risk, the lack of an effective mechanism for drug prevention in the anti-drug policy of international institutions and most countries, Gavrikova Anastasia Vladimirovna, Kireeva Irina Leonidovna, Toropygovna Aleksanra Vyacheslavovna and others are still working on this issue. It should be noted that serious research is needed in our country;

- addiction, as a negative phenomenon, requires the elucidation of the phenomenal aspects of this concept. This, in turn, is a requirement of the time for a theoretical study of the meaning and interdependence of the concepts of "addiction", "drug addiction" and "narcotism", in particular, the study of its origin, definition, etymology from a socio-philosophical and political point of view. It is important to determine the essence. "First determine the meaning of the word," advised R. Descartes, "then you will save people from half of the mistakes they make" [20];

- the fact that the problem is covered on the basis of historical principles has helped to understand the essence of its content, the research of ancient Greek scholars, as well as the analysis of a number of scientific literatures on the subject.

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